

**STATUS OF HOUSING AND HOUSEHOLD AMENITIES OF
TEA TRIBE POPULATION - A CASE STUDY IN THE
BISWANATH DISTRICT, ASSAM**

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Abstract:

The provision of housing is considered to be the most fundamental need of mankind. The present study intends to focus on the status of housing condition and existing household amenities of Tea Tribe (Adivasi) population in the Biswanath district of Assam. Tea Tribe is considered as the most socially and economically downtrodden community in the state of Assam as well as in the district of Biswanath belonging to Mundas, Santhals, Orangs etc. tribes of exogenic origin.. During colonial rule they had migrated from different states of Central India to work in the tea gardens of Assam. The Tea Tribes are treated as other backward caste (OBC) in Assam. Their original ST status which they have been accorded in their respective states of origin from where they migrated is yet to be accepted by the State of Assam. Tea Tribe community comprises 20 percent of total population in Assam. As per housing condition is concerned majority of them are living in dilapidated dwelling structures devoid of essential and minimum basic amenities for living such as electricity, provision of sanitary toilet facilities, provision of drinking water supply and smokeless fuel for cooking etc. The study emphasizes to focus on the issues and problems faced by the Tea Tribe population who remarkably contributes towards the development of the tea industry of Assam but often their stories of pain and agony are unheard and go unnoticed. Even the Government policies fail to reach majority of them rather they are wooed and used as vote banks at the time of election.

Key Words: Housing, Basic amenities and dilapidated dwelling and socially backward.

1. Introduction:

The very existence of man depends upon the fulfillment of his three basic or fundamental needs i.e., food, clothing and shelter. Adequate shelter or in other words a house is a fundamental pre-requisite for each and every human being in terms of safety, security, self- esteem, social status, cultural identity, satisfaction and achievement. In fact, access to shelter and hygienic living conditions are crucial to human well-being as they directly determine the quality of life. A suitable home with adequate living rooms, access to sanitation, drinking water and electricity is important to every family of both rural and as well as urban areas. But most of the families cannot construct such a house with their own resources and thus are being deprived of minimum basic amenities of living. In the district of Sonitpur of Assam the problem of adequate housing is more acute in rural areas particularly among the socio-economically deprived groups. Most of the poor households lack minimum basic amenities such as provision of sanitary toilets, access to safe drinking water, cooking fuel and electricity. The possession of a shelter with all necessary amenities cannot be a dream of a poor man in the wake of the rising prices of the building materials, scarcity of land, financial crisis and the rapidly growing population. Despite of the fact that Government has implemented various housing schemes and policies in rural areas for solving housing problems yet it has made very limited progress and has failed to reach at grass root level. In this study an attempt has been made to understand the problems and issues related to housing among the Tea tribe population from a better perspective.

2. Review of Literature:

Smith and Thorns (1978) explained that the housing is one of the three basic needs of human beings, but it is still beyond the access of the disadvantaged section of the society." Majority of the households in the rural areas are lacking the minimum basic amenities of life. In this context, Stephen and Laquian (1979) expressed that "the most striking manifestation of rural poverty is the poor quality of their housing". Joshi (1997) throws light on "the housing as a big challenge to society. Demand-supply gap in housing spheres shows that it is in short supply for both rural and urban settlements. Shelter-less people are looking for government built houses. Besides kutcha (non-durable) houses are being converted into pucca (durable) houses by economically forward moving groups". Mukherjee (1996) suggested that "the poor households should be provided with basic infrastructural facilities like safe drinking water, sanitation and draining of sewages, power, road and transport. The poor households should participate in designing and planning the construction of their houses, its implementation and maintenance. It is only then, the poor households would experience improvements in their housing conditions in real sense of term". According to Seventh Five year plan (1987-1992), the development of housing must enjoy top priority in a society such as ours where housing amenities are far below the minimum standards that have been internationally accepted.

Rao (1979) made a comprehensive study on housing in the developing countries. He suggested that "a radical change is needed in the housing policies of the government to solve the housing problem".

3. Objectives of Study:

The present study is carried out on the basis of following objectives mentioned below-

- ✓ To understand the problem of housing and shortage of adequate household amenities like electricity, drinking water sources, sanitary toilets and domestic fuel for cooking in the tea tribe households.
- ✓ To suggest measures for effective planning so that better habitable environment can be provided to the socio-economically downtrodden sections of the society particularly tea tribe population.

4. Methodology:

The study has emphasized mainly on the socio-economic status of the rural population considering their housing conditions and access to basic amenities and sanitary conditions. For this purpose, data is obtained from both primary and secondary sources to supplement in making general observations. Primary data is collected at the village level with the help of questionnaires, interviews of village headmen and door-to-door household survey. The simple random sampling technique is used for the purpose of household survey. The sample size is taken as 30.00 percent so that it represents adequately the Universe of the district. For the study, three blocks (Sakomatha, Biswanath and Pub-Chaiduar) out of the total seven blocks in the district is considered for study. For detailed study, three villages having dominance of tea tribe population are selected from each of the selected blocks i.e. Koylajuli, Bhimajuli and Gogra basti villages respectively. Altogether 120 households i.e 40 households from each blocks belonging to Tea Tribe population are considered for study. The data collected from field has been classified and tabulated into simple and cross tables, showing percentages for an analytical study.

5. Study Area:

The Biswanath district of Assam covers an area of 1100sq. km on the North bank of river Brahmaputra. It is declared as district on 15th August 2015 and bifurcated from Sonitpur district. The district is bounded by Golaghat district on the south, Arunachal Pradesh on the north, Lakhimpur district on the east and Sonitpur district on the east. The administrative headquarter of the district is located in Biswanath Chariali. The district has seven developmental blocks- Baghmari, Behali, Biswanath, Sakomatha, Sootea, Chaiduar and Pub-Chaiduar. There are 947 numbers of villages in the district with total rural population of 780567 as per census 2011. The district is a home of various ethnic tribes and communities. Mishings, Bodo, Rabha and Deuri are major indigenous tribes of the region. The Tea tribe population constitutes nearly 20 percent of the total population of the district and provides cheapest labour forces to the tea cultivation. Among all the social groups in the region the Tea Tribes are the most deprived and unprivileged section from the social and economic perspectives. Massive illiteracy, ignorance, poverty, unemployment, alcoholic addiction and superstition etc. are the factors responsible for their backwardness.

6. Findings of Study:

6.1 Qualitative Assessment of Housing:

Housing Structure: The standard of housing cannot be assessed merely in quantitative terms; rather qualitative assessment of housing is utmost necessary to evaluate the standard of living and quality of life in real sense of term. In fact, the quality of houses goes a long way in improving the quality of life. Although every rural household has some sort of dwelling to live in, but a large chunk of the people live in houses which are below the minimum acceptable standards. It should however be noted that the quality of housing can also be assessed by referring to the provision of safe drinking water, electricity, type of fuel used, availability of separate kitchen and toilet facilities. Apart from that the available minimum assets in the households can also measure the economic conditions and quality of life. To understand the above aspect data has been generated related to durability and quality of houses. As mentioned in previous chapter, that the type of housing can be classified mainly into three types on the basis of the building materials used in the construction of wall, roof and floor. These are:

- ✓ Pucca houses are those whose walls, floor and roofs are constructed with durable and concrete materials like cement, iron rod stone, sand, bricks, tiles, iron sheets etc.
- ✓ Semi Pucca houses are those whose either wall, floor or roofs is constructed with non durable materials like mud, sand, dung, bamboo, wood etc. while rest is constructed using durable items
- ✓ Kutcha houses are those whose wall, roofs and floors are constructed with non durable and locally available materials like bamboo, wood, thatches, leaves, mud, dung etc.

Table 1: House types of tea tribe population across sampled blocks

Blocks	Total Sampled Households	Kutcha	Semi Pucca	Pucca
Sakomatha	40	14(35%)	19(47.5%)	7(17.5%)
Biswanath	40	16(40%)	16(40%)	8(20%)
Pub-Chaiduar	40	19(47.5%)	16(40%)	5(12.5%)
Total	120	49(40.83%)	51(42.5%)	20(16.66%)

Source: Field Survey, 2015-17

The table 1 shows that around 40 percent of total households belonging to tea tribe population have kutcha dwelling structures and only 16.66 percent have pucca dwelling structures for stay. This pattern more or less reflects the fact that economy of the households determines the types (qualitative) of housing pattern rather than social or cultural effect on the same. At the same time, the type of dwelling based on pre-dominant materials used in construction determines the standard of living and exhibits the income level among the social groups. Pucca or concrete houses resemble stability or permanency and better housing conditions compared to the Kutcha and Semi-pucca dwellings. During the survey it is found that around 25 percent of kutcha houses are in a dilapidated conditions and needs immediate replacement. While interrogating with the respondents regarding the benefits of housing schemes like IAY, PMAY etc. they reported that their names are not registered under BPL list and so there are deprived of such benefits. This is mainly because of political favoritism and corruption at ground level. Only 20 percent of the respondents are benefitted by the housing schemes.

Household Amenities:

Availability of Electricity: Modern world without electricity is incomplete. The availability of electricity to every household is their right.

Table 2: Availability of electricity in the households across sampled blocks

Blocks	Total Sampled Households	Electricity Available	Percent	Electricity Not Available	Percent
Sakomatha	40	26	65	14	35
Biswanath	40	32	80	8	20
Pub-Chaiduar	40	21	52.5	19	47.5
Total Households	120	79	65.83	41	34.16

Source: Field Survey, 2015-17

Even today there are millions of households in India which are not connected with power lines. Like other parts of Assam, the Biswanath district is also lagging behind in rural electrification. The table 2 shows that around 34.16 percent of the households are found to be still not well connected by the electric power grids and depends partially or fully on kerosene and other means for lighting. Only 65.00 percent of households belonging to tea tribe population in the district are connected with power lines.

Source of Water Supply: The availability of water for drinking, maintenance of personal hygiene, performing household chores and satisfying needs of livestock is the minimum basic requirement of every household. But surprisingly, even today there are some remote villages in the district where some poor households are facing the crisis of adequate access to safe drinking water.

Table 3: Distribution of households according to the type of water source across sampled blocks

Blocks	Total Sampled Households	Tap Water	Protected Well	Unprotected Bore Well	Hand Pump	Public Water Point	River/Pond/Tank
Sakomatha	40	2	6	11	9	8	4
Biswanath	40	3	5	14	7	9	2
Pub-Chaiduar	40	0	5	10	5	8	12
Total Households	120	5 (4.16%)	16 (13.33%)	35 (29.16%)	21 (17.5%)	25 (20.83%)	18 (15%)

Source: Field Survey, 2015-17

It is seen from the table 3 that around 29 percent of tea tribe household depends on unprotected bore well and nearly 15 percent depends on river or pond or streams as water source for consumption and other household chores which make them more susceptible to serious water borne diseases. While interrogating with the members of sampled households it is found that those households who do not have tap water within their household premises, are found to be also depended on alternate sources like ponds or rivers if available nearby as more water is required for laundry, livestock and other household chores. Non-availability of water source within the household premises may be hazardous for health at the same time. When the water is collected, it has to be transported and stored in some vessels. The stored water increases the risk of water borne diseases such as diarrhea, jaundice, typhoid etc. and provides the breeding ground for mosquitoes and thereby poses the risk of malaria and dengue. It is found in the survey that the risk of diarrhea diseases is the one of the leading cause of deaths among the children under five in most of the Tea Tribes dominated villages of the district. Moreover, the vessels where the drinking water is stored have to be cleaned regularly and should be covered with a lid. But in some households it is seen that they keep the vessels uncovered which is harmful for health and results serious diseases. It is particularly due to lack of awareness regarding the health and hygiene. Even if the water is available within the household premises, the sources of water supply must be protected and freed from pollution. But most of the time, it is seen that the water sources are much polluted in some of the sampled households in the study area. The unprotected water sources are open to contamination and pose a potential health risk.

Type of Fuel Used for Cooking: Traditional fuel for cooking is being dominantly used by the poor households particularly in the rural areas. Burning of biomass fuel for cooking in open fire stoves and with little ventilation, generates huge amount of smoke containing large quantities of harmful pollutants which may have serious health implications particularly to women as they are directly involved in cooking and also to infants or young children who stays with their mothers even while cooking meals for household members. At the same time, the massive use of fire wood as fuel for cooking has an adverse impact on environmental resources particularly forest, leading to a situation of rapid deforestation and as well as loss of biodiversity and man-elephant conflict especially in Assam. From the table 4 it is noticed that only 25.83 percent of household has access to cleaner fuel like LPG while the rest are dependent on the traditional fuel like firewood, crop residue and cow dung cakes for cooking purposes and thereby exposing themselves to harmful pollutant emitted while burning. Low income restricts the poor households to switch over to the cleaner fuels for domestic uses.

Table 4: Type of fuel used for cooking in the households across blocks

Blocks	Total Sampled Households	Firewood & Crop Residue	LPG	Dung Cakes
Salomatha	40	24	11	5
Biswanath	40	18	14	8
Pub-Chaiduar	40	30	6	4
Total Households	120	72(60%)	31(25.83%)	17(14.16%)

Source: Field Survey, 2015-17

The type of fuel used and location of kitchen has combined effect on health as well. If the type of fuel used for cooking is traditional then it will definitely emit harmful pollutants and the location of kitchen within the living room itself without partition with little or no ventilation will obstruct the release of polluted air from the cooking stove and thus will affect health particularly to women and infants. During survey, it is found that the incidence of acute respiratory diseases and eye irritation is more common among rural households as majority of them are dependent on biomass as cooking fuel. To get an overall picture regarding the health of tea tribe households and to find the strong association between the biomass fuel combustion and the high incidence of respiratory illness in the study area, data was collected from the records of 10 primary health care centers servicing the remote tea tribe inhabited villages covered within the study area is taken into consideration. The total number of patients treated in last six months by these primary health care centers for respiratory diseases and eye infections and average number of patients per public health centers is shown in table 5

Table 5: Type of diseases registered in the primary health centers in the villages

Diseases Type	Total Patients	Percentage of Male Patients	Percentage of Female Patients	Percentage of Child Patients (0- 12 Years)
Bronchitis	2053	64	73.5	6
TB	899	4.3	5.2	0.4
Asthma	575	7.5	8.6	0.2
Pneumonia	35	1.5	2.4	0.3
Cough	90	56	65	17
Phlegm	38	4.4	3.2	1
Blood in Sputum	12	3.4	5.5	1.7
Eye Irritation	1457	56	72	15
Skin Infection	51	3.2	9.3	5.3

Source: Field Survey, 2015-17

From the table 5, it is revealed that high incidence of respiratory illness and eye infection are found among women particularly those who are actively involved in cooking and also among children between age group of 0-10 years in the study area. Bronchitis and eye irritation is the most common disease observed in the study area as per the report collected from the health centers. On an average around 47.83 percent of patients are affected by Bronchitis and 47.66 percent of patients are affected by eye related diseases. While 9.9 percent of patients are affected by Tuberculosis, 16.3 percent are suffering from Asthma, 46 percent are suffering from prolonged cough, 2.8 percent are affected by phlegm, 3.5 percent are affected with bloody sputum and 5.93 percent are affected by skin infections. It is reported by the local health practitioners and doctors in these health centers that the cause of increased incidences of respiratory illness and eye irritation specially among women and children is due to exposure to harmful smoke emitted while burning of biomass fuel used for cooking meals.

To reduce in consumption of biomass, the government should make the distribution system of cleaner Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG), kerosene and solar energy more viable and accessible to the BPL families residing in the rural areas. However, the current Government attempt to light the flame of poor's kitchen with the cleaner fuel like LPG has thrown a ray of hope to the aspirations and desires of rural people to freed themselves from the harmful effect of poisonous gases emitted every time in their kitchen while cooking meals. Thus, the introduction of Ujjawala Yojana to provide LPG cylinders to every rural BPL female headed families

is praiseworthy. But the complete success of this policy will definitely depend on its strategic implementation at the grass root level.

Provision of Sanitary Toilets: Sanitation is considered as the yardstick to measure the quality of life and to assess the socio-cultural and economic progress of any region. The word ‘sanitation’ generally refers to the provision of facilities and services for the safe disposal of human excreta and household waste either in the form of liquid or solid in order to make the nation and as well as every community free from diseases and to provide a healthier environment for all. But even today some parts of the country are facing an acute crisis of adequate sanitation in both rural and urban areas. The availability of a sanitary toilet at home is the one of the essential basic amenity for every household from the point of view of health and hygiene. Open defecation or absence of proper sanitary toilets at home endangers every member of households to various types of diseases. In rural areas the magnitude of problem is large as 34 percent of the rural population in the district defecates in the open compared to 18 percent in urban areas. The absence of toilet within the household premises is affecting the lives of women and they are risking themselves to various communicable diseases like malaria, dengue etc and non-communicable diseases like gastro-intestinal infections, water borne diseases etc.

Table 6: Availability of toilets in the households across blocks

Blocks	Total Sampled Households	Have Toilet Facility	Percent	Do Not Have Toilet Facility	Percent
Sakomatha	40	11	27.5	29	72.5
Biswanath	40	13	32.5	27	67.5
Pub-Chaiduar	40	9	22.5	31	77.5
Total Households	120	33	27.5	87	72.5

Source: Field Survey, 2015-17

From the table 6, it become evident that nearly 70 percent of tea tribe household in the district have no access to toilet facility and prefers to defecate in the open. The idea of building some sort of facility for defecation in or near the house unfortunately does not attains priority among tea tribe population in rural Assam. Interestingly, it is found during survey that the households which do not have toilets possess mobile phones and TV sets. In fact, the lack of awareness regarding the probable health impacts from open defecation is the main cause behind such unhealthy practices. Open defecation is a common practice among the tea tribes despite of certain households being facilitated by the tea garden authority or government organizations. As the district is largely covered with tea gardens so the problem of defecation acts as a big challenge. It is found in the survey that hundreds of publicly funded toilets are left unused because of their mindset to defecate in open fields. Thus, the need of the hour is to spread awareness regarding health and hygiene among different backward and downtrodden sections in the district.

7. Discussion:

7.1 Analysis of Socio-Economic Determinants: The above discussion portrays a dismal picture about the status of living conditions of the Tea Tribes households in the district. Low income, poor employment, low wage rate, high rate of indebtedness, lack of awareness about health and hygiene is the factors to be blamed for this.

Table 7: Monthly income of Tea Tribes households across blocks

Blocks	Total sampled Households	HIG (Above Rs.10,000)	MIG (Rs. 5,000- Rs. 10,000)	LIG (Below Rs.5,000)
Sakomatha	40	6	12	22
Biswanath	40	9	18	13
Pub-Chaiduar	40	8	14	18
Total Households	120	23 (19.16%)	44 (36.66%)	53 (44.16%)

Source: Field Survey, 2015-17

Note: HIG = High Income Group, MIG = Medium Income Group and LIG = Low income group.

Here an attempt has been made to analysis the socio-economic determinants responsible for poor housing condition and low access to basic amenities in the Tea Tribe households in the district. From the table 7, it comes to the light that the economic condition of thr Tea tribes households in the district is not sound as nearly 45 percent of the households belongs to low income group category and 36.66 percent belongs to medium income group category respectively. Only 19.16 percent of households belong to high income group class. This indicates their backwardness in terms of economic condition which is primarily responsible for their poor living conditions.

Table 8: Occupational Structure of Tea Tribes Households across blocks

Blocks	Total Sampled Households	Farmer	Agricultural Labour	Allied Agricultural Activities	Non Agricultural Activities	MNGREA Worker	Government Service
Sakomatha	40	12	8	4	6	8	2

Biswanath	40	4	13	6	7	9	1
Pub-Chaiduar	40	4	11	6	9	10	0
Total Households	120	20 (16.66%)	32 (26.66%)	16 (13.33%)	22 (18.33%)	27 (22.5%)	3 (2.5%)

Source: Field Survey, 2015-17

The occupational structure reveals the income of the households. The Table 8 shows the occupational structure of the households among Tea Tribe population across blocks in the district. It is revealed that around 56.65 percent of the households are engaged in agricultural activities. The percentage of households engaged as agricultural workers is nearly 26 percent because most of them have either less or no agricultural holdings. It may be important to mention here that as the agricultural labourers suffered from seasonal unemployment for most part of the year, so they engage themselves as daily wage earner for the rest of the year during off season particularly after harvesting and sowing of paddy cultivation in rural construction and reconstruction work as MGNREGA workers.

Non- agricultural activities in the surveyed area includes daily wage earning activities, small retailing, shops, vending, Rickshaw puller, driver or handyman, factory or company worker, carpentry, masonry, weaving, artisans etc. It is also seen in the Table 8 that 18.33 percent of the total sampled households are engaged in non-agricultural activities. Again, it may be mentioned here that the beneficiaries of MGNREGA (a scheme under central government to provide wage-employment to the rural unemployed youths) got to work for maximum of 100 days in a year. So, the agricultural workers who suffered from seasonal unemployment are found to get engaged as MGNREGA workers with a wage rate of Rs. 200 per day which is very low.

Table 9: Rate of indebtedness of households of different income groups

Income Groups	Total Households	Indebtedness (%)
HIG	23	17.54
MIG	44	34.04
LIG	53	51.67

Source: Field Survey 2015-17

It is a fact that a household lying under the burden of debt cannot prosper economically. The high rate of indebtedness determines the poor economic condition of a household. Table 9 showed the rate of indebtedness among different economic groups. It becomes evident from the Table that the rate of indebtedness is highest among the LIG households (51.67%) and lowest among HIG households (17.54 %) respectively as expected. The rate of indebtedness among MIG households is found to be 34.04 percent a common problem among the middle class people. Thus, it is revealed that the high rate of indebtedness among LIG households is equally responsible for their poor economic conditions.

8. Recommendation:

Low cost housing technology must be adopted through the judicious utilization of locally available building materials along with improved skill and innovative technology which can reduce the construction cost of a house within affordable budget. Cleaner fuels like LPG should be made available at subsidized rates to each and every household in rural areas so that the burden of collecting firewood by females and children can be lessened and they can spend their valuable time in doing some productive works. Awareness programmes regarding sanitation and hygiene practices among the downtrodden and backward sections of the society should be conducted. However, Government efforts for successful implementation of sanitation and health programme in rural areas will be more meaningful if greater emphasis much be laid on women's education. At the same time for promoting hygiene and to make villages open defecation free there is a need to provide free low cost toilets to poor households.

Accessibility to drinking water to the economically vulnerable sections must be tackled in effective ways so that every household have access to sufficient quantities of water. The Government should provide public water points in backward villages. Housing loans at subsidized rates should be provided to rural poor by Government and public funding agencies if he/she wants to construct or expand building. Skill based education and technical training must be provided to the youths belonging to the tea tribe population so that they become capable enough to start their self business and thereby become financially independent. The deep rooted beliefs that a child born in a tea tribe family is destined to become a tea garden worker must be eradicated through quality education and awareness amongst them.

9. Conclusion:

Tea tribe population provides cheapest labour to the tea industry of Assam. The tea industry is considered to be the backbone of the economy of Assam. But unfortunately, the Tea Tribes are the most unprivileged social group in the state and as well as in the district of Assam living in a miserable condition and their households are deprived of minimum essential amenities for living. We cannot imagine of overall development if a particular section or group in our society are deprived economically and socially. It must be admitted that a good housing leads to good health and good education and is a reflection of social identity and

self respect. Thus, it is the need of the hour to provide the socially downtrodden sections particularly Tea Tribe population with a quality life through quality housing with all essential needs for survival. This demands a successful implementation of housing policies designed specifically for the poors considering their needs at the grass root level intervening political loopholes.

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